

The Spatial Patterns of Airbnb Offers, Hotels and Attractions:
Are Professional Hosts Taking Over Cities?
Supplementary Materials

Abstract

This paper includes the results of the empirical analysis assuming that the latitude-longitude values of Airbnb locations are discrete and accurate.

Table 1: Global Moran's I statistic

	Airbnb	p-value	Hotels	p-value	Attractions	p-value
Barcelona	0.71	0	0.36	0	0.64	0
Berlin	0.6	0	0.57	0	0.61	0
London	0.55	0	0.4	0	0.58	0

Table 2: Bivariate Moran's I for various pairs of variables

	Airbnb - Hotels	p-value	Attractions - Airbnb	p-value	Attractions - Hotels	p-value
Barcelona	0.34	0	0.49	0	0.4	0
Berlin	0.33	0	0.5	0	0.52	0
London	0.42	0	0.38	0	0.42	0

Table 3: Pearson Correlation for various pairs of variables

	Airbnb - Hotels	p-value	Attractions - Airbnb	p-value	Attractions - Hotels	p-value
Barcelona	0.37	0	0.54	0	0.39	0
Berlin	0.34	0	0.64	0	0.66	0
London	0.84	0	0.54	0	0.56	0

Table 4: Bivariate Moran's I for hotels and non-professional or professional listings

	Hotels - NP	p-value	Hotels - P	p-value
Barcelona	0.25	0	0.34	0
Berlin	0.24	0	0.36	0
London	0.24	0	0.43	0

Table 5: PC in the case of hotels and non-professional or professional listings

	Hotels - NP	p-value	Hotels - P	p-value
Barcelona	0.25	0	0.37	0
Berlin	0.23	0	0.38	0
London	0.45	0	0.87	0

Table 6: Bivariate Moran's I in the case of attractions and non-professional or professional listings

	Attractions - NP	p-value	Attractions - P	p-value
Barcelona	0.42	0	0.47	0
Berlin	0.43	0	0.5	0
London	0.23	0	0.39	0

Table 7: PC in the case of attractions and non-professional or professional listings

city	Attractions - NP	p-value	Attractions - P	p-value
Barcelona	0.44	0	0.52	0
Berlin	0.55	0	0.63	0
London	0.34	0	0.55	0

Figure 1: LISA: Airbnb (left) and hotels (right)

Figure 2: LISA: non-professional (left) and professional (right) listings

Figure 3: Bivariate LISA: Hotels - NP (left) and Hotels - P (right)

Figure 4: Bivariate LISA: Attractions - NP (left) and Attractions - P (right)

